

CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

Device Closure of Large Tubular Patent Ductus Arteriosus(PDA) with severe Pulmonary Hypertension: Analysis of Five Hundred and Twenty Cases

Nurun Nahar Fatema*

*Armed Forces Medical College and CMH Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Introduction: Patent ductus arteriosus (PDA) is one of the most common congenital cardiac defect observed in many surveys around the world. The incidence of isolated PDA has been estimated as about 10-12% of all varieties of congenital heart disease. In a study in CMH Dhaka, 18% of congenital lesions are recognized as PDA. A large (Complicated) PDA can cause severe pulmonary hypertension (PHT) either due to increased pulmonary blood flow or increased pulmonary vascular resistance (PVR). It is a common cause of heart failure in infancy.

Background: Large tubular PDA cases are usually referred to cardiac surgeons. Because of severe pulmonary hypertension, these cases were refused by surgeons in Bangladesh in the early part of beginning of subspecialty. Percutaneous closure of PDA was started in Bangladesh in 1998. Device closure of large tubular PDA was started since 2007 and successful outcome encouraged to continue the intervention as first choice therapy.

Aim: To see the outcome of device closure of large tubular PDA with severe Pulmonary Hypertension. **Materials and methods:** It is a retrospective study conducted in Combined Military Hospital CMH Dhaka and Lab Aid Cardiac Hospital. Total 578 patient reported with PDA from Jan 2007 to Dec 2019 Period. All the cases had been selected from history, Physical examination, chest X-ray, ECG, 2-D and Doppler Echocardiography. Median age was 7 months (17 days to 65 years), median weight 4.5 kg (2.2 to 62 Kg), 76 cases had down syndrome and 99 cases had Congenital Rubella Syndrome (CRS). Narrowest PDA diameter was 1.8 to 14 mm, Median 6 mm, 340 cases were female and 238 were male. Pulmonary: systemic blood flow various from 1.1:1 to 6.7:1 in room air. Pulmonary vascular resistance ranged from 4.5 to 12 wood units. Pulmonary arterial pressure ranged from 60/40(46) to 170/90(105) mm of Hg. Systemic pressure ranged from 60/45(49) to 180/95(110) mm of Hg. With 100% oxygen pressure was reduced in 554 cases and was same in 34 cases. Minimum device size was 5/4 mm, maximum 20/18 mm. Most commonly used device was ADO from Lifetech scientific followed by Cookon, MFO and ADO11.

Result: complete Occlusion was achieved in 562 cases. RV Pressure reduced to normal by three months in all except three.

Conclusion: Transcatheter closure of PDA cause minimum hemodynamic impairment even in tubular large cases and it may be performed as outpatient basis in children more than one year of age. It can be performed safely under deep sedation. In our centre we keep the patient in observation ward for 24 hours. An Echocardiography is done routinely before discharge. This study supports that huge tubular PDA with severe PHT can be closed safely in all age groups with conventional devices with some alteration and modification of shapes or with double disc devices. However we will follow up these cases up to three years to observe the long term outcome of all cases.

Keywords: Patent ductus arteriosus, Tubular device closure.

*Presenting Author

Professor Nurun Nahar Fatema. She has passed MBBS in 1985 & FCPS in Pediatrics 1995 and trained in Prince Sultan Cardiac Center in Riyadh, KSA in Pediatric Cardiology from 1996 to 1998. Later trained in Australia, UK, USA, India etc. Awarded with FRCP and FACC in 2009 and FSCAI in 2011. Working as Chief Pediatric Cardiologist of CMH Dhaka since 1998 and HOD pediatrics since 2014 and Professor & HOD paediatrics of Armed Forces Medical College and . Professor Fatema is the pioneer Pediatric Cardiologist of Bangladesh . She performed more than 7000 pediatric cardiac interventions and innovated many new techniques in cardiac interventions. Her NNF protocol for PPHN and cyanotic spell is widely used and saving life of hundreds of newborn and children. She has about 100 publications in different national and international medical journals. She has participated in more than hundred national and international seminar and presented scientific papers.
